

Table 2. Mean and standard deviation for six traits in the population of protoclonal lines compared with control lines.

Trait	Control lines		Protoclonal lines		Significance of the differences at 5% level (Fisher t test)	Miara protoclonal lines/Miara control lines ^b
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Days to flowering	91.1	1.4	88.7	1.8	NS ^a	Later**
Fertile tillers (8 plants)	64.6	16.2	67.9	13.7	NS	Fewer**
Plant height (cm)	98.1	2.8	89.9	6.5	S	Taller**
Panicle length (cm)	17.3	0.3	18.9	1.2	NS	Longer**
Grain length (mm)	9.1	0.12	9.4	0.22	NS	No difference
Grain width (cm)	2.9	0.06	2.9	0.07	NS	Wider**

^aNS due to difference in earliness between the two replicated experimental plots. ^bFrom Mézencev et al (1995); ** = significant at the 1% level.

were scored for six traits along with control lines in a replicated field experiment (Table 2). Overall, the range of variation observed among the Ariete protoclonal lines was much narrower than that in the protoclonal population generated from Miara following the same experimental procedures, though it remained for most traits wider than that of the control line population.

A unidirectional drift toward earlier, shorter, and longer grained lines was observed. The mean of the protoclonal lines differed significantly from that of the control lines for plant height, and 22 and 44% of the lines exhibited significantly shorter culms and longer grains, respectively. On the other hand, we found no significant difference in fertile tillering, grain width, and panicle length between protoclonal and control lines.

This limited occurrence of variation among the protoclonal lines contrasts with our previous results from evaluating Miara protoclones in the field (Table 2). These findings, along with the analyses of other reports, confirm that the range, direction, and frequency of variation is more related to the genotype than to a given tissue culture procedure.

Cited references

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- Mézencev N, Clement C, Guideroni E. 1995. Variation among progenies of diploid plants regenerated from haploid, microspore-derived haploid cell suspension protoplasts of rice (*Oryza sativa* L.). *Plant Breed.* 114:149-154. ■

AC, with long, slender grains) and japonica (highly responsive to AC, with short, thick grains) genotypes. We examined F₁ (and their corresponding reciprocal), F₂, and BC populations with one BC to each parent. The cosegregation of AC response and grain type was evaluated.

The diallel study indicated that the low AC response shows incomplete dominance with respect to the high response. Thus, the AC response in the F₁ generation is below that of the most responsive parent (Table 1). Possible maternal effects—although not statistically different—were only noted in the crosses when CT8707 was used as the nonresponsive parent (Table 1). The generation mean analyses suggest that simple (oligogenic) genetic systems of different sets of genes control callus induction and green plant regeneration. For callus induction, additive and dominant effects were highly significant, whereas for green plant regeneration, only additive effects were statistically significant (Table 2).

The cosegregation analyses indicate that callus induction ($c^2 = 0.853$) and green plant regeneration ($c^2 = 0.978$)

Table 1. Anther culture response of crosses between japonicas CT6241-17-1-5-1 and Todoroki Wase, and indicas IR43 and CT8707.^a

Parent or cross	Callus anther ⁻¹ (%)		Green plants callus ⁻¹ (%)	
IR43	0.0	d	0.0	d
CT8707	0.0	d	0.0	d
CT6241	19.8	b	43.9	a
Todoroki Wase	42.2	a	28.8	b
IR43/CT8707	0.0	d	0.0	d
CT8707/IR43	0.0	d	0.0	d
CT6241/Todoroki	58.3	a	28.3	ab
Todoroki/CT6241	65.2	a	23.2	ab
CT8707/Todoroki	2.2	bcd	0.0	d
Todoroki/CT8707	15.9	bc	3.3	cd
CT8707/CT6241	6.6	bcd	3.3	cd
CT6241/CT8707	11.8	bcd	0.0	d
IR43/Todoroki	15.4	b	12.3	bc
Todoroki/IR43	17.9	b	12.8	b
Todoroki/IR43 F ₂	12.7	bc	11.7	b
Todoroki/IR43//IR43	5.2	c	7.2	c
Todoroki/IR43//Todoroki	24.9	b	17.6	b
IR43/CT6241	13.9	bc	11.9	bc
CT6241/IR43	13.4	bc	22.1	b
CT6241/IR43 F ₂	4.5	cd	7.5	b
CT6241/IR43//IR43	5.4	c	7.9	b
CT6241/IR43//CT6241	12.3	bc	15.9	b

^aMeans with the same letter are not significantly different according to the Waller-Duncan K-ratio test, $p \leq 50.01$.

Toward introgression of high response to anther culture into indica rices

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Anther culture (AC) is routinely used in our program to reduce the generation time for broadening the genetic diversity of breeding gene pools and to facilitate molecular tagging of genes. Most of these applications have been mainly restrained to crosses containing at least one japonica parent due to the recalcitrance of indica genotypes.

Replacing sucrose with maltose and adding silver nitrate to the callus induction medium substantially increases the AC response of indicas (Lentini et al 1995); however, the yield of doubled haploids per anther from indicas is still about 20-fold less than that from japonicas. Evidence exists that a few genes control AC response in rice (Miah et al 1985, Quimio and Zapata 1990). Therefore, the introgression of the high AC response from japonicas into indicas could facilitate applying AC as a routine tool for breeding indica rice.

We conducted diallel and backcross (BC) inheritance analyses using crosses between true indica (nonresponsive to

Table 2. Generation mean analysis based on data from the populations P₁, P₂, F₁, F₂, BC indica, and BC japonica of the crosses Todoroki/IR43 and CT6241/IR43. ^a

Parameter ^b	Callus anther ⁻¹		Green plant callus ⁻¹	
	Todoroki/IR43	CT6241/IR43	Todoroki/IR43	CT6241/IR43
[m]	7.02* ^c	-5.11	16.29**	21.02**
[a]	20.75** ^c	9.12**	15.72**	21.46**
[d]	10.29*	20.33**	-1.58	-3.86
[axa]	13.79**	14.76**	-	-
[axd]	-	-	-17.85**	-28.19**
[dxd]	-	-	-	-
χ ² (2df)	1.20	3.70	3.90	4.10
P	0.55	0.16	0.14	0.13

^a According to the simplest model that explains the observed values. ^b [m] = mean value between parents, [a] = additive effects, [d] = dominant effects, [axa], [axd], and [dxd] interactions between additive and/or dominant effects. ^c *, ** = different from zero at p = 0.05 and 0.01, respectively.

segregate independently from the grain type. Plants combining high response to AC from the japonica parents (up to 70% callus induction and 90% green plant regeneration) and grain type from the indica parents (up to 8.7 mm long

and 2.9 mm wide) were recovered as early as in the F₂ generation and, subsequently, in the BC indica generations.

Twenty lines with high response to AC and long, slender grains were selected. We are evaluating individual pro-

genies from each selected line for its in vitro response and agronomic characteristics. Selected plants will be used as parents in crosses with plants from a recurrent selection population to develop a genetically diverse indica gene pool with increased response to AC.

Cited references

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Random mating of composite populations for improving restorers in rice

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Most commercial indica hybrid rices have been developed through the wild abortive (WA) cytoplasmic male sterility (CMS) system, which involves using CMS (A), maintainer (B), and restorer (R) lines. Desirable restorer lines should possess good fertility restoration ability, high performance, multiple disease and insect resistance, good general combining ability, high pollen production and/or dispersal, and good grain quality. Hybrid rice breeding programs continuously need these lines to breed superior hybrids.

Most hybrid rice breeders usually select R lines among elite lines bred by inbred breeding programs where crosses are generally made without considering the parents' restoration abilities. Alternatively, R lines are also developed from R × R or A × R crosses specifically made for this purpose. Thus, frequency of R lines among a group of breeding lines depends on the

Procedure used at IRRI to develop random mating composite populations for improving restorer lines.